

Navigating Aberrant Root Canal Anatomy: A Case Series on Complex Variations

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Abstract

An in-depth understanding of root canal anatomy and its variations is essential for achieving endodontic success. This case series highlights the endodontic management of teeth exhibiting complex anatomical variations: a mandibular molar with confluent middle mesial canal, a mandibular molar with radix entomolaris and a mandibular premolar showing Vertucci Type V configuration. The cases were diagnosed and managed using enhanced visualization through a dental operating microscope. Thorough exploration of the pulp chamber floor, ultrasonic troughing and meticulous cleaning and shaping techniques enabled successful location, negotiation and obturation of these aberrant canals. Postoperative follow ups showed favorable outcomes in all cases. This series underscores the importance of clinical vigilance, appropriate use of technology and anatomical knowledge in managing a typical canal configurations to ensure long-term treatment success.

Keywords: Anatomical Variaton, Middle Mesial Canal, Radix Entomolaris, Vertucci Type V, Gulabivala Type I, Sert and Bayirli Type XVIII

Introduction

The prerequisite of any endodontic therapy is to have familiarity with the root canal anatomy of the tooth. Proper and accurate interpretation of radiographs taken at different angulations, especially using the paralleling technique, is crucial for diagnosing the number of roots and root canals in a tooth. Identifying all the portals of exit, debridement of the entire root canal system and sealing all the exits with three dimensional filling materials make endodontic treatment successful.^[1]

Clinically, mandibular molars exhibit a wide range of anatomical variations, including the presence of additional roots such as a distolingual (radix entomolaris) or mesio-buccal root (radix paramolaris), C-shaped canal configurations and complex root canal systems with three canals in either the mesial or distal roots. These may include a middle mesial canal (MMC) or a middle distal canal (MDC), both of which can follow various morphological patterns.^[2]

The incidence of having an extra canal in the mesial root is 1-15%.^[3] Pomeranz et al., in 1981, classified the middle mesial canal into three types, namely: A fin, A confluent, and an

independent type.^[4]

Carabelli was the first one to mention the presence of an additional root in mandibular first molar and called it as radix entomolaris (RE).^[5] Literature suggests the presence of RE in less than 5% population in white Caucasian, African, Eurasian and Indians whereas it is present with a frequency of 5–30 % in races with Mongoloid traits such as the Chinese, Eskimos, and Native Americans.^[6]

Pulp space is complex, root canals may divide and rejoin. Depending upon the configuration, root canal may exit apically through one or more than one apical foramen. Some mandibular first premolars show Vertucci type V canal configuration accounted for only 1.5% to 6.66%.^[7]

Several classifications have been proposed to describe root canal configurations for communication. Some of which we will discuss in this case report will be Vertucci FJ (1984), Gulabivala K et al. (2001) and Sert and Bayirli (2004).^[8]

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This case series highlights the clinical management of three mandibular teeth with complex anatomical variations.

Case Report

Case 1: Management of Middle Mesial Canal in mandibular first molar with root canal configuration classified under Gulabivala K et al Type I (3-1) and Sert and Bayirli Type XVIII (3-1)

A 26 year old male patient reported to Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, with the chief complaint of pain in his lower right back tooth region since a week. The pain was intermittent, exacerbated by the intake of hot food and beverages and persisted for 2-3 hours. Clinical examination revealed deep proximal caries in the right mandibular first molar, with otherwise satisfactory oral hygiene. Pulp sensibility testing revealed an exaggerated and lingering response to the heat test, indicative of symptomatic irreversible pulpitis.

A preoperative radiograph showed a radiolucency involving enamel and dentin, approaching the pulp. Periapical radiolucency was observed in intraoral periapical radiograph, indicating periapical lesion in relation to mesial root.

Case 1: Middle Mesial Canal

Treatment Procedure

Inferior alveolar nerve block (IANB) was administered using 2% lignocaine hydrogen chloride (HCl) with 1:2 lacs units of adrenaline (Lignox, Indoco Remedies Ltd, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India). The access cavity was prepared by endodontic access bur size 2 (Dentsply-Sirona, Charlotte, North Carolina, United States) under rubber dam isolation. The access cavity was refined using Endo-Z bur (Dentsply-Sirona), exploration of the pulp chamber was done using an endodontic explorer and the canals were negotiated using a size 10 K file (Mani, Inc., Japan). Three canals were initially located, two mesial and one distal.

Ultrasonic tips (Start-X, Dentsply-Sirona) were used to explore the MMC orifice and the canal was negotiated using a size 10 K file. The working length was determined using Apex locator (Root ZX mini, J. Morita Inc, USA).

Finally, a total of four distinct orifices were identified and verified using magnifying loupes (iMag™, Vision Forward LLP, Mumbai, India): Mesially three (MB, middle mesial, ML) and distally one. The Middle mesial canal orifice was found near to mesiobuccal canal orifice and all three mesial canals converged apically to exit as a single canal.

The shaping and cleaning were carried out by ProTaper Universal NiTi rotary instrument (Dentsply-Sirona) in a crown-down manner till F2(25/8%) and distal with F3(30/9%).

Copious Irrigation was carried out using 3% sodium hypochlorite solution (Prime Dental Products Private Limited, Thane, Maharashtra, India), Endoprep-RC (Anabond Stedman Pharma Research Pvt Ltd, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India) and saline. Canals were dried using paper points and obturation was done using single cone technique with bioceramic sealer (MTA fillapex, Angelus, Brazil). The mesiobuccal canal was obturated first followed by mesiolingual and then middle mesial canal up to the point of convergence.

Post-obturation radiograph revealed three distinct mesial canal orifices, merged in the apical third and exited as one. The access cavity was restored using a composite restoration (3M™ ESPE Filtek™ Bulk Fill, 3M, St. Paul, Minnesota, United States).

Case 2: Re-Treatment of Radix Entomolaris in mandibular first molar

A 32-year old male patient reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics with the chief complaint of persistent dull pain in the lower left back tooth region for the past 10 days. The discomfort was continuous in nature, with occasional episodes of sharp pain aggravated during mastication and intake of hot beverages.

The patient gave a history of prior root canal treatment in the same tooth approximately 6 months back, which had provided temporary relief. However, over the last few days, the pain had intensified. On clinical examination, tooth presented with restoration and tenderness on vertical percussion. Oral hygiene was fair.

A preoperative intraoral periapical radiograph revealed previous root canal treatment with inadequate obturation and presence of an additional root distally. Another radiograph was taken at mesial and distal angulation to confirm the same. A distinct periapical radiolucency was observed in the distolingual root, suggestive of apical periodontitis.

Case 2: Radix Entomolaris

Treatment Procedure

Access cavity preparation was done under local anesthesia with an endo access bur (Dentsply, Switzerland). Subsequent isolation of the area with a rubber dam, the occlusal filling was removed. A total of four canal orifices were identified and verified using magnifying loupes (iMag™, Vision Forward LLP, Mumbai, India). The removal of gutta-percha was accomplished

through the utilisation of retreatment rotary files (ProTaper Universal Retreatment Files, Dentsply Sirona).

The determination of working length was conducted using an apex locator (Root ZX mini, J. Morita Inc, USA) and afterwards verified through radiographic examination using a 10 K hand file (Mani, Inc., Japan). The canals were prepared using ProTaper Universal NiTi rotary instrument (Dentsply-Sirona) in a crown-down manner till F2(25/8%). The canals were irrigated using a solution consisting of 2.5% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl), 17% Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), 2% Chlorhexidine (CHX) and saline solution. The application of intracanal medicine, specifically calcium hydroxide (CH) paste was applied using Lentulo spiral (Dentsply Maillefer) size 25. Access cavity was closed with a cotton pellet and a temporary cement Cavit (3M ESPE). Patient was scheduled for next visit after 1 week.

After 1 week, the tooth was asymptomatic and the temporary filling was intact. Following the rubber dam isolation, the temporary cement and cotton pellet were extracted from the access cavity. The use of 2.5% NaOCl in combination with ultrasound activation was done effectively to eliminate the CH paste present in the root canal. The experimental procedure concluded with a final rinse utilizing a solution of 17% EDTA for a duration of 1 minute.

Canal was dried with a paper point and obturated using Gutta percha with single cone technique and bioceramic sealer (MTA fillapex, Angelus, Brazil). Patient was recalled after one week for complete coverage restoration.

Case 3: Management of mandibular first premolar with Vertucci Type V (1-2) root canal configuration.

A 24 year old female patient presented to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics with the chief complaint of intermittent pain in the lower left posterior region for the past week. The pain was dull, occasionally sharp and aggravated on chewing and cold beverages. On intraoral examination, a deep occlusal carious lesion with tenderness on percussion was observed. Pulp sensibility testing revealed exaggerated and lingering response to cold, suggestive of symptomatic irreversible pulpitis.

Thorough radiographic examination revealed existence of single root with one canal in coronal region dividing into two separate canals in middle third region, suggesting a Vertucci type V root canal configuration. Radiolucency was observed involving enamel, dentin and extending to the pulp chamber, without periapical involvement.

Case 3: Vertucci Type V (1-2) configuration

Treatment Procedure

Access cavity preparation was done under local anesthesia with an endo access bur (Dentsply, Switzerland). First a #10K file inserted in buccal canal, the next #10K file was pre-curved and inserted in a distolingual direction to traverse the canal bifurcation into the second canal.

Working length was taken using an electronic apex locator (Root ZX mini, J. Morita Inc, USA) and an IOPA radiograph was also taken to confirm the presence of a single coronal canal bifurcating into two separate canals. Biomechanical preparation was done with protaper rotary instrument upto # 25/04 file. Irrigation procedure was carried out with 5.25% NaOCl, 17% EDTA and saline solution. Canals were dried using sterile paper points and gutta-percha master cones corresponding to the size of master apical file were inserted to the full working length. Obturation was done using single cone technique with buccal canal first followed by lingual canal using AH plus sealer (Dentsply Sirona). The tooth was restored with composite resin (Ceram.X Spectra™ ST HV (Dentsply Sirona, Konstanz, Germany).

Discussion

Clinical triad of diagnosis, adequate chemo-mechanical preparation and three dimensional obturation determine the success of root canal therapy. Endodontic re-treatment requires addressing a series of challenges that may be morphological or iatrogenic, such as under extended access cavity, filling materials or foreign objects.^[9]

Critical evaluations of multiple angulated radiographs help the operator better plan the endodontic treatment. A study done by Chavda et al. showed that magnification predominantly helped in identifying the thin MMC, along with ultrasonics. MMC are very tiny and may be present deep into the isthmus.^[10]

In our report, Case 1 had an confluent type MMC. Based on the Pomeranz et al.'s classification, a confluent canal implies that it originates separately but merges with either the mesiobuccal or mesiolingual canal before exiting the root, appears as an additional orifice but does not exit independently, which is found to be rare.^[11] Toubes et al. stated that the MMC orifice was closer to MB (46%), followed by ML (31%), and found separately between MB and ML (23%).^[12]

In Case 2 of this report, Type 1 radix entomolaris was seen. The radix can be classified based on the root/canal curvature, proposed by Ribeiro et al.^[13]: Type 1, straight root/root canal; Type 2, initially curved entrance followed by straight root/root canals; and Type 3, curvature at coronal third followed by buccally oriented curvature starting from middle to apical third.

The exact etiology of radix entomolaris is still not known but according to some authors it may be due to disturbance during odontogenesis or may be due to the high degree of genetic penetrance.^[14]

In Case 3, preoperative radiographs showed a distinct narrowing in the middle third of the canal, prompting further

investigation, which eventually confirmed the presence of a Vertucci Type V configuration. Miyoshi et al. concluded that variation in canal anatomy may be suspected when the middle third of the root appears equal to or greater in diameter than the coronal third on a preoperative radiograph.^[15] Similarly, Yoshioka et al. indicated that a sudden narrowing or abrupt loss of canal continuity on a parallel radiograph is often suggestive of multiple canals.^[16]

The clinical success of endodontic therapy hinges on recognizing and treating anatomical variations that may otherwise be overlooked. This case series reinforces the need for careful radiographic interpretation, use of magnification and thorough exploration of the pulp chamber floor. Identifying uncommon variations such as middle mesial canals, radix entomolaris, and bifurcating premolar canals ensures complete debridement and obturation, preventing failures and enhancing long-term prognosis.

Conclusion

The complexity of the root canal system often presents a challenge to clinicians. Undetected anatomical variations can compromise the prognosis of endodontic treatment. This case series demonstrates how careful identification and management of complexities such as middle mesial canals, radix entomolaris, and Vertucci Type V configurations, can lead to improved outcomes. Clinical vigilance, combined with advanced techniques and a thorough understanding of root canal anatomy, remains essential for endodontic success.

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